

The Impact of English Language Teaching Methods on Academics through Digital

Material

Mrs.Md.Roshan Jameer¹ Dr.K.Venu Madhavi² Dr.N.Prasanna Lakshmi³ Mr.Ollala Srinivas⁴

¹Associate Professor in English Avinash Degree College, KPHB Hyderabad

²Associate Professor Material Development Testing and Evaluation School of ELE, EFLUH Hyderabad

³Assistant Professor of English GITAM Deemed to be University Hyderabad

⁴PGT English, Telangana Minority Residential School Karimnagar Boys-3,TS

Email mroshan19@gmail.com

Email- ollalasrinivas@gmail.com

Abstract- As we are living in the information age the most important aspect of lifelong learning and development is language. People skills like reading, writing, speaking, listening (LSRW skills) enquiring, comprehending and problem-resolving are smartly managed with language skills. Information and communication technology has been claimed as the best tool in the English language teaching and learning process. This research paper highlights how the digital materials effect teaching methodology towards academic success. It aims at how students are benefitted with the replacement of old teaching methodologies with digital materials. English aspirants have a variety of methods to supplement their students for sharpening their interpersonal skills.

Introduction:

Nowadays, classrooms are equipped with interactive whiteboards (IWB), response systems, projectors, and computers. Many reputed universities and organizations are introducing this digital tool to enhance their English language skills. Many topics of the English language can be clearly explained and taught through this channel. Improvement of technology has led to many new inventions that English language teachers began to use in education. Social, psychological and emotional development can be attained through English language learning. Students can interact with people, convey their emotions, thoughts and easily connect with the external world, through the process of language acquisitions. Modern age brings developments which are useful for the students helping them with their jobs and everyday activities. The use of modern language teaching aids like digital materials for the English language learners is one such change in modern age. Whiteboards and markers are replacing the blackboard and chalk system, physical lectures are further enhanced by direct live lectures through the World Wide Web, seminars are transformed into webinars and for any sort of language queries, online English language Instructors are always available.

Review Literature:

P.C.Naga Subramani and V.Iyappan, Tamilnadu Teachers Education University, Karapakkam, Tamilnadu discusses in their journal "Innovative methods of teaching and learning" (2018) that innovative methods and tools of teaching-learning methodologies are available across the

globe. Short lectures, stimulation, portfolio development and problem-based learning are very useful in swift technology used at the education system as well as workplaces in the foreseeable future. Bureu Okmen, Abdurrahman Kilic, Duzce University, Turkey in his journal "The Effect of Language Teaching Methods on Academic Success in Turkey"(2016) opines that English Language affects the characteristics of individuals. He discussed that language skills must not be confined to the classroom education given at the school level. New approaches and methods to improve people's language skills must be implemented by every educational organization.

V. Raymond Lesikar in his book "Business Communication" indicates how the present technologies and trends can be blended together while keeping the fundamentals of the language intact. It helps in reducing communication relating issues, development of audience and gives a lucid picture of visuals and the English language.

Fennel(2001:267) as cited in Kenning(2007) states that the English language is treated as killer language, communication technology will be the major weapon.

Nurul Nadia Haron and Yasmin Hanafi Zaid, University Technology Malaysia discusses the various methods to educate through web-based learning like online journals, educational movies.

Objectives:

The main aim of this study is to understand how digital teaching materials effect the pedagogical method of education in this progressive era. The study also discusses the role of digital materials

towards the personal growth of an individual as well as achieve academic success for any profession.

Discussions And Methodologies Adapted:

Introducing digital learning in the curriculum is benefitting the English aspirants in the real sense. This sophisticated teaching approach spurs the students to achieve their required targets in the fastest and unique manner. In the past centuries, teaching tools were of various kinds and teachers adopted myriad materials to educate the students like Sand, Stones, Leaves, and quills, the bark of a tree, blackboard and chalk. And in the recent past, we can see Printed materials in the form of academic books. But advances in science and technology have revolutionized the present-day world. The technology has made a remarkable place for itself in imparting education to young minds. Technology can be adopted at any level beginning from primary school, middle school, high school or up to the university level. It has transformed the traditional classroom into e-learning or digitalized class rooms such as Google classrooms. Wherein students have ample scope to learn and interact with different people across the globe. Students can learn about different subjects and cultures. They can also learn about the effectiveness and usefulness of learning the English language for the purpose of communication in their native lands or as a foreign language.

Modern Teaching Aids:

Teaching aids are something that makes teachers feel easier to teach their students. Their by training them to learn in a more enjoyable and effective manner. List of modern teaching aids are discussed below:

WEBINARS: [Webinar Centric]

A blend of words like web and seminar together is termed as Webinar. It can also be addressed as a web event, webcast/ web lecture/ virtual event. It is generally performed through the internet by the online audience. It offers various interactive opportunities like asking a question, chat, poll, test, call to action, twitter. The average viewing time for webinars currently stands at 56 minutes. The benefits of webinars offering to us are: can have direct contact and interaction with the target group. It saves time and money. By conducting WEBINARS, students can probe deeper into real problems and try to face the professional challenges. They express their point of view through this platform in the best possible way. Webinar post-click landing page examples to the model are:

- Kissmetrics.

- IBM Watson.
- Microsoft.
- Microsoft Azure.

Presentation Tools:

Attractive PowerPoint Presentation through different slides is another important component of Modern Teaching Aid [MTA] for English language aspirants. Google Sites, Prezentit, Animoto, Vuvox, Viddix, Vcasmo, Preezo can assist students, Research scholars and English language Teachers to view their ideology in any projects of their research study. Users of PPT can effectively express their thoughts with captivating slides instead of real objects. Fennel (2001:267), as cited in Kenning (2007), claimed that "If English is to be seen as a "Killer" language, communication technology must be interpreted as one of its major weapons." Therefore, it is interpreted from the above a statement that students can learn the English language by using technology by not relying too much on the teacher's ability to engage them in classroom.

Voice Threads:

Currently, many web-sites make provision for uploading PowerPoint slides, videos, photos, etc. and also add voice narration to design multimedia presentations. One such web-service is "Voice Threads." It built and engages students to transform a cluster of media files, such as documents, images, videos and presentations to a convenient place so, that everyone can access easily. Educators make use of Voice Threads for documentary classroom conversations to online tutoring, professional development training. It's one of the great ways to deliver assignments or projects and get feedback. One can attain detailed information about Voice threads through following web links like:

Blogging-[Public Post]:

Students can use this Blogging for practicing their study session. They can post their notes on the class blog, where one can access, evaluate and rewrite a new material. Teachers may have a track of record to modify their actions. Our thinking can be crystallized through Blogging.

Prezi- Presentations:

To make professional like presentations, a versatile app like "Prezi" can be accommodated, as digital material. It's more usable and capable of covering advanced features compared to PowerPoint Software. It's new and can be easily accessible. Fresher can dive and flow easily through the entire app fairly well and produce nice-looking presentations. This app assists presenters to design embellished presentations with audio and video notes in it.

Social-Bookmarking:

Researchers or educators who have similar interests can have easy access through these useful websites like Bookmarking. There is one more great advantage of this app like it allows the user to save the bookmarks to our favourite folder automatically. And the unique flexibility is, it allows us to access and retrieve the bookmarks saved in any computer device, other than the one which we saved. So storing and searching is made an easier task by this useful resource.

Podcast in classroom learning:

This feature of the digital app is not only resourceful to the common users but also much useful to physically challenged people like hearing impaired students. Podcasts provide serial recordings of oral lectures and news shared regularly online for the listeners. It is flexible and reusable technology available for reversing the oral lecture.

Screencast:

Screencast is an amazing instructional digital tool. It is a highly effective, powerful and affordable teaching-learning aid that can cater to education across any curriculum. Screencast procures a step-by-step methodological approach with data detailing theirs by enriching PowerPoint presentation along with narration and multimedia elements. Trainers of the English language can avail of the free software available on websites to instruct or train their students. Some of the freebies available are Screen jelly, Jing, Screen which facilitates learners to express in the most captivating way without wasting much time.

Moodle:

Moodle is a digital teaching-learning material that facilitates a virtual learning environment both teachers as well as learners to access. Ever note is a useful tool to explore and organize the research content.

Impact of social media into education:

Some well-known social communities in websites are Twitter, Face book, YouTube, blogs and My Space. The challenges by above cited social media are:

- Providing unnecessary information
- Losing control over data
- Commitment towards time is not attained

To keep students engaged, pooling students through social-media can generate resource to make understand and take feedback from the students or users of it.

Smart boards:

Instructional efficiency to smart products is brought by the instructors by making course content virtual and interactive to all.

Research Tools:

The most productive website links for any research scholars for equipping themselves and have a better result in their field of research are yolink, veezzle, specify, nibipedia, findthatfile, dogo etc.

Mobile Assisted Language Learning: [Mall]

Information technology in the form of digital material has provided many online or offline MOBILE APPS for comprehensive learning in the easiest way. LSRW skills can be well practiced and learnt at their own pace with this novel approach. Listening and speaking skills can be improved by the students who can't afford regular lectures. Audio tools like Audacity, Wavosaur, Chiribit, Raper, Vocaroo, Audio Pal, and Sound Cloud can enhance their listening and conversational skills a lot. It saves time and money for the students who live in the remote areas. Students can retain the learnt content for longer time and English language teachers can help students by providing speech training to the pupils through VIDEO RECORDINGS. This sort of teaching aid makes the abstract ideas concrete and thus help in making learning more effective. Business Correspondence is one of the most demanding aspects of the business entrepreneur. Constructing clear statements in English language and responding to the messages can be well trained through many resources. To mention a few, certain writing tools like: NetEditor, Smories, Student Publishing, FlipSnack, Mixboot are the variety of teaching materials available, to train the students how to draft the business communications. From any authoritative websites 'Readymade Templates and Wizards' can be availed by the students for effective correspondence.

Teachers can substitute real objects to training aids like videos, DVDs or videotapes to help students make learning equally meaningful. To create healthy competence among the students, English language trainers can encourage

Quiz and Poll Tools: Students learn to face the typical mindsets and quick approach to recall the relevant stuff at that point of participation. To train such competitive spirit tools like Kubbu, Quibble, What2learn, Quiz Egg, eQuizzer are more useful.

Benefits:

- Technology has brought radical changes in teaching-learning tools by grabbing student's interest in it.
- Digital materials provide PBL-Problem Based Learning which is very useful to the student community.
- Smart gadgets facilitate different tasks such as teaching, framing question papers, assessment of students' performance and feedback.
- Advance pedagogy creates rich experience for students as well as a rewarding experience to the educators.
- Hybrid teaching model combines both e-learning as well as face to face teaching. Such synchrony helps to teach and to learn in their systemic approach of study. In this way, out of class learning can be encouraged.
- Teaching learning with technology stimulates and engages students and trainers to accomplish their objective learning.
- By incorporating digital teaching and learning materials we can save money, labour and time
- Our Curriculum could be extended by adopting technological content knowledge to the teachers and learners to enhance professional and academic skills.
- New age education system is able to imbibe four key skills in the students, which include 4C's: Communication, Collaboration, Competition and Creative and Critical Thinking skills.
- It helps educator or facilitators to view education in a constructive way.
- It helps facilitators in differentiative instructions and value based assessments.
- NES-is trying to inculcate in students, values with a tinge of skill development.
- From Gurukul age to digitalization age, there has been a big leap, where teaching includes not only sending information but also receiving.
- Usage of digital materials or unique technology tools helps to grab and sustain the attention of students while pursuing their higher education.
- Digital tools help the students to perceive, comprehend and retain. Therefore helping them in learn and relearn
- The facilitator can make the content of the curriculum Concise, Crisp and Captivating for the students in their learning process.
- With the digitalization- organizations also reap the benefit of recognition in long list of acclaimed schools, colleges and reputed Universities.
- Digitalization provides the apt platform for Self-Assessed learning, thereby making classrooms making "Student-Centric.
- E-learning bestows equal opportunities to educate and learn, to harness their skills on a regular basis.
- Communication via e-mode gives students significant insight into their given situation.
- Web based learning tools give the flexibility to the student mob to complete the task outside the classrooms, yet connect to the classrooms.
- E-learning tools have eliminated the barriers of time and cost, as the students save the cost of travelling.
- Universities can attract more students register through online-learning
- E-learning, builds the confidence of a student, as they are given the opportunity to broaden their knowledge at their own pace.
- Online learning tools- give ample scope to the learners, to control their own learning process.
- Modern tools make students independent, as he/she has scope to eliminate unnecessary information and concentrate on required data.
- Students might overcome the insecurities that usually they face in classroom learning through this new mode of education.
- Online education material makes the content and format, easily adaptable to changing times.

Barriers:

Apart from the above mentioned multiple benefits in adopting-developing-adapting digital material in enriching the curriculum-based teaching and learning with technology. There are many hindrances to overcome and embellish the English language learning easier. To mention a few:

- Students should have prior knowledge, in the usage of technology otherwise it may effect the success of the e-learning environment.
- For students, who prefer their mother-tongue mode of communication may find it difficult to navigate as it is based generally in the English language.
- E-Learning is difficult to adopt, as it involves human skills, to be specific motor skills.
- The initial stages of an e-learning tool are time- consuming as the students find an alien culture of learning to be adopted

- Web-based learning may be apt only for students with self-discipline, as it depends on independent focus to understand the topic.
- Digital learning tools encourage, students to have prior training, which may be a barrier to gain knowledge through this innovative mode.
- E-learning materials expect students to have a focussed, which is a challenging task for their age.
- The negative impact of e-learning on the facilitators is that their creativity is side-tracked and not recognized.
- Digitalization has spoon-fed the students, which kills their cognitive skills.
- Unlike the traditional classroom learning process which is fun-filled, the e-learning curriculum may become monotonous, confining to individual four walls.
- Generally the human brain has data retention ability which is far more superior to artificial intelligence, but intervention of digital learning mode is degenerates the ability to store and retrieve. Due to excessive dependency on machines rather than using human intelligence.
- It became a bane to the young minds, confining them to four walls. Thereby giving the experience of Social isolation.

Conclusion:

Summing up, Technology based learning and teaching tools may be a boon to curriculum only if it doesn't ruin the chief objective of education process. The researchers or educators should aim at transforming the true essence of knowledge or information to the mediocre. With the adoption of modern tools, the young minds and facilitators can adorn the English language acquisition into limelight. At the same time, teachers as well as students should bypass the old system of learning and

teaching modes and experience the new spur of education.

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